

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth System**

Fast-Track data delivery on ice dynamic fluxes

Milestone MS5

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The image on the cover sheet	Nico Grütter, Pixabay

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The data have been made available to the consortium partners on 28 July 2023 on the project server of partner ETT for download via an FTP.

Work Performed

Several individuals were involved in this work: The key contributors are Romain Millan (RM), Jean Baptiste Barré (JBB), Gael Durand (GD), WP3 leader and Nicolas Jourdain (NJ), WP2 leader. All collaborators designed the methodology, RM and JBB collected and processed the data, NJ evaluated the format for ocean modelers.

The team provided an evolution analysis of ice shelf basal melting. This included a netcdf file containing a spatially distributed map of basal melting rates and associated errors, with a resolution of 500 meters, reprojected on the bedmachine grid. Additionally, they produced two CSV files containing ice-shelf integrated basal melt rates and related errors. These variables cover a time span from 1992 to 2017 on a yearly basis. Furthermore, the team also delivered an analysis of ice shelf calving fluxes. They provided a gpkg file containing ice shelf integrated calving fluxes, as well as a netcdf file depicting the spatial distribution of calving across ice shelf fronts. The latter was achieved by utilizing ice velocities and reprojecting the results on the bedmachine grid.

First, the data resulting from this work have been distributed to WP2 for the evaluation of the format for ocean modellers. The data have been shared with the partners in the consortium through a FTP server made available by partner ETT.

Looking ahead, the dataset will undergo testing by ocean modellers, to be performed by WP2 staff. Depending on the direct feedbacks of ocean modellers, this product will be further improved with the adjustment of the dataset's format, temporal resolution, and grid spacing to meet specific requirements (e.g., model domain, geometry, projections). This adaptability is essential to cater to the diverse needs of different modelling approaches. In that sense, a routine for dataset regridding will be developed in collaboration with ocean modellers. This routine will automate the process of regridding the dataset based on user-defined model setups, streamlining the workflow, and facilitating its integration into various modelling frameworks. Finally, the collection and calculation of new basal melting maps from additional satellite sensors coming from photogrammetry (Worldview, ASTER), and other satellite altimeters (e.g., Cryosat-2) will be explored for improving the spatial resolution (<500 m), in the case of local modelling applications in targeted regions of Antarctica (e.g. Amundsen sea). Ultimately, this work will feed into the deliverable D3.1 ***Contributions of ice sheet processes to freshwater fluxes*** due in April 2024, the D3.1 deliverable is public and thus all the data will be made available in open access, in full compliance with the OCEAN:ICE data management plan.